

PHILOLOGY

THEME OF ARTICLE (PECULIARITIES OF FORMATION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE)

Kismetova G.,

*Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor
West Kazakhstan University named after M. Utemisov*

Baimukanova A.

*Master's student of the philological faculty,
West Kazakhstan University named after M. Utemisov*

Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to clarify the remote development method of foreign language communication skills in modern foreign language teaching methodologies. This paper attempts to highlight the relevance of remote methods of foreign language communication skills development using Zoom software. This paper gives a distance method for developing communicative competence in a foreign language. Considerable attention is paid to techniques such as discussion, conversation, brainstorming, social, and psychological.

Keywords: method, development, foreign language communication competence, Zoom, programme.

Introduction

In the theory and practice of foreign language education in the Faculty of Linguistics, one of the most important elements of education is to develop students' professional language skills through foreign language speaking situations. The professional level of foreign language proficiency remains an important social determinant, requiring further improvement and development of language teaching systems in higher education institutions with key language teaching profiles. Courses in foreign language teaching at language universities are primarily of a professional orientation. University graduates must acquire that level of foreign language proficiency in order to become a good expert in the language of their chosen specialty.

Foreign language learning in today's global education system is positioned as a tool for practically solving and coordinating social and occupational problems and issues, rather than the theoretical nature of acquiring knowledge, skills, and abilities. Students in higher education institutions that focus solely on the transfer of theoretical knowledge face the harsh reality that they are ill-equipped to work independently and seriously in complex social situations. The educational standards categorize university academic fields into majors, basics, general, and so on. The knowledge acquired in the major categories also depends on the extent to which the foreign language is integrated into practical professional activities. Thus, for language college students, mastery of a profile of a subject such as "foreign language" is the primary result of implementing the requirements of state federal standards, and the primary goal of this section of the standard is to Because it is to form communication skills.

Analyzing the linguistics higher education standards, it can be concluded that one of the main aspects of undergraduate professional education is communicative competence. These include the ability to correctly search and process primary information, the ability to prepare abstracts, reports, and papers for conference

presentations, and the expansion and enrichment of social and language experiences that will serve as the basis for future professional activities.

The word "competence" appeared in the field of education because in the world of work, it is evaluated whether an excellent employee meets certain standards. The concept of "linguistic competence" was first introduced by N. Chomsky within the framework of generative linguistics, and is based on the knowledge of language as a means of communication for an ideal speaker rather than a real speaker, and for communication practice.[3]

In the modern situation where higher education in Kazakhstan is being integrated into the world educational space, one of the most important requirements for university graduates in almost all fields is effective professionalism in the modern multicultural and multilingual world. It is the knowledge of a foreign language that enables meaningful interaction.

In Kazakhstan higher education institutions the attention to teaching language disciplines is conditioned by the adopted Concept of multilingual education, which is understood as a purposefully organized, standardized triune process of education and upbringing of a multilingual personality. This result can be achieved by mastering several languages simultaneously. The Kazakh language (mother tongue) as a state language, Russian as the language of international communication, and English (world language) as the language of integration into the world economy are defined in the Concept. In Kazakhstan today the Kazakh-Russian bilingualism actually functions. The promotion of English to this level should become the norm not only for Kazakhstan's elite, - it is noted in the Concept, where the trajectory of education is determined by a polylingual approach.[6]

The issues of the essence of forming communicative competence and competence approach in the pedagogical process are considered in the works of Kazakh scientists V.A. Kim, B.A. Zhetpisbaeva [7].

In her work, S.S. Kunanbayeva emphasises that "it is necessary to note the ambiguity of the term 'intercultural competence', which is understood as a subject of training in the field of foreign language teaching, in the sense of intercultural communicative competence". However, the same term is also used in a broader sense. That is, it is used in the field of cultural studies as intercultural competence, which refers to the ability to manage intercultural communication, or intercultural communication, which refers to communication between representatives of different cultures. The revision of the theory and practice of foreign language teaching has pre-determined updated and targeted foreign language teaching. The updated goal setting is manifested in a new end result - the formation of intercultural communicative competence as a person's intercultural communicative competence, defined as the subject of intercultural communication. Intercultural communicative competence is realised through a series of sub-competences: cognitive competence, communicative competence, linguistic-cultural competence, socio-cultural competence, conceptual competence and personality-centredness. [5]

At present, the issue of the formation of communicative competence is little studied. There is much controversy and disagreement on this issue.

The most detailed description of communicative competence, according to L. F. Bachman [1], includes linguistic, discursive, conversational, pragmatic (practical), sociolinguistic, strategic and mental competence, according to the scientist's theory.

According to Geikhman, D. Himes, L. F. Bachman at the centre of communicative competence has five main elements:

1. linguistic competence - knowledge of lexical units and of the grammatical rules that transform lexical units into meaningful statements
2. sociolinguistic competence - the ability to select and use the appropriate language forms and means according to the purpose and situation of the communication and according to the social role of the participants in the communication, i.e. who their communication partners are.
3. discourse competence - the ability to understand different types of communication statements and to construct coherent and logical statements in different functional styles (articles, letters, essays, etc.) Language means must be selected according to the type of utterance.
4. strategic competence - the linguistic and non-linguistic means (strategies) that people resort to when communication does not take place. Such means may be both re-reading phrases, questioning misunderstood statements, gestures, facial expressions and the use of different objects.
5. socio-cultural competence - knowledge of the cultural characteristics of native speakers, their customs, traditions, codes of conduct and etiquette, and the ability to understand and use them appropriately in the process of communication. The formation of socio-cultural competence involves the integration of the individual into the world and national cultural system.

In order to form students' foreign language communication skills outside the language environment, it is not enough to fill English classes with communicative exercises that enable them to solve communicative tasks. Conditions need to be created in which future professionals have the opportunity to think creatively, solve some problems, reason in English about possible ways to solve problem situations and concentrate on the content of their statements. It is important to improve the communicative skills of speaking a foreign language and expressing one's ideas. Therefore, the goal of learning should not be the foreign language itself, but speech activities in the foreign language.

Now let's consider the main methods of remote training of communication skills in college students.

Zoom, kahoot, e-mail gmail.com, and google classroom were used for the purpose of remote development of communication skills of first-year linguistics students. Each program serves a unique function for the remote formation of foreign language communication skills.

In particular, the Zoom platform was used to run online classes.

Zoom is a cloud-based video communications app that allows you to set up virtual video and audio conferencing, webinars, live chats, screen-sharing, and other collaborative capabilities.

You don't need an account to attend a Zoom meeting, and the platform is compatible with Mac, Windows, Linux, iOS, and Android, meaning nearly anyone can access it.[4]

Zoom is used for online and practical lessons to develop vocabulary, grammar and communication skills. Zoom allows students and teachers to see each other, creating a traditional classroom atmosphere.

Zoom offers the following features.

1. individual or group high-resolution voice and video calls.
2. chat, which allows Zoom to quickly send messages and capture students' attention using Mentions
4. send presentations, photos and other materials to your screen during a call using the integrated screen sharing feature.
5. Zoom can be installed on any device, including phones, computers and tablets, so students can learn English anywhere using a variety of partial devices.

During the pandemic, the Zoom platform was active. It was very convenient for us, so that's why we used it for the experiment.

The practice was conducted among undergraduate students. Methods such as discussion, brainstorming, conversation, social and psychological training were used in the classroom to develop students' communicative competence in foreign languages. Let's look at each method separately.

1. A discussion is a discussion of a controversial issue or problem. An important characteristic of discussion, which distinguishes it from other types of disputes, is argumentation. When discussing a controversial issue, each party opposes the opinion of the other party and argues for its position [1].

Discussion also refers to the collective discussion of any problems, controversial issues. A discussion is

often seen as a method that intensifies the learning process, the study of a complex topic, a theoretical problem.

The following exercise was sent to the students in the chat room:

Express agreement/disagreement with the following statements using the following speech patterns. Argue your opinion. Model: a) I fully agree with the statement. I think... b) I am afraid, I can't agree with it because...

1. Not everything we do is governed by some set of rules.

2. We need rules that everyone must obey.

3. Laws against criminal conduct don't help to safeguard our personal property and our lives.

4. It is impossible to resolve disputes peacefully.

5. Totalitarian governments have cruel and arbitrary laws.

6. Laws should be applied to every person in the society.

7. The only goal of the law is fairness.

The purpose of this technique is to activate your communication skills. The main function of discussion in developing communicative competence is to stimulate cognitive processes.

Discussions are effective after introducing new words and grammatical structures. Discussions help you reinforce and cement the vocabulary and grammar you have learned. Discussion method can be done by video call

2. Conversation - The main function of this method is to stimulate, but other functions can be equally successful. In practice, conversational methods are used to solve complex problems, such as learning new material, establishing material, developing creative abilities, and shaping academic ability in general, allowing students to understand problems from multiple perspectives.

3. Brainstorming is a creatively stimulating problem-solving technique that asks participants to express as many solutions as possible, including the most fantastic ones. Then, from the total number of ideas expressed, the best idea that can be used in practice is selected. In brainstorming, criticism is not allowed, and any idea, whether humorous or silly, is encouraged. All ideas submitted are written down and later reviewed by a panel of experts. Once a decision is approved, the "idea-makers" are divided into opponents and proponents to identify and fix weaknesses [8].

We brainstormed remotely by setting up a group conference with the participants in the lesson and talking about the problem and having the students come up with ideas.

Think-pair-share. To use this method of brainstorming more effectively it was necessary to allow time for the students to think for themselves. Then ask them to discuss the ideas in pairs with others in the classroom, and then bring the ideas to the group discussion.

Example: What qualities do we need to be a successful lawyer? The pupils did the following steps:

1) Analyse solutions to the problem on their own (1-2 minutes).

2) Suggest and discuss ways of solving the problem with a talker (1-2 minutes).

3) Introduce and discuss ideas as a group (2-4 minutes).

4) Identify the most appropriate ideas.

4. Socio-psychological training is a method of active learning and psychological influence that takes place in the process of intensive group interaction and aims at enhancing foreign language competence in the area of communication, where the general principles of learner activity are complemented by principles of consideration of one's own behavior and that of other group participants [2]. In this training, you can learn effective techniques (methods, techniques, techniques) for management decisions and business communication, clarify the individual characteristics of participants, and correct their behavior in communication situations. In addition, during the training, participants will acquire communication and decision-making methods and skills according to their individual characteristics. When participants become emotional during training, their motivation to learn increases, knowledge retention, and skill and ability formation are strengthened.

Hot Spot. After studying a chapter or a new topic, we carried out this exercise. Beforehand, students were chosen to be presented to the others as experts. The task of the experts is to answer the students' questions on the topic covered. During the course, the experts would change. It is possible to organise a reverse system of this method, i.e. to choose a few students who will prepare a series of questions for the other students. Anyone may answer the questions. The hot-spot method not only effectively develops language competence but also psychologically prepares students for socialisation and business communication. Example: Unit 1 "Law and legal professions" Ask questions about law and legal professions.

-Which legal professions do you know?

-What is law?

-Why do we need law?

-What qualities do we need to be a successful lawyer? etc.

Conclusion

Analysis of theoretical and methodological scientific literature and experiments with first-year students reveal five basic components of communicative competence and four basic methods of remote formation of foreign language communicative competence: discussion, conversation, and brainstorming, social and psychological methods were revealed. As a result of the experiment, it became clear that using an integrated approach is the most rational way to develop and form the communication skills of college students. It is a combination of teaching methods. Each method has advantages and limitations. Proper combination and application of remote methods for building foreign language communication skills will lead to more effective high-level foreign language communication skills, namely, the ability to act in various situations, self-introduction and public speaking skills, and active listening skills, the ability to assert one's opinion, and so on.

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TYOLOGY OF METHODS OF TRANSLATING RAY BRADBURY'S PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS INTO RUSSIAN (BASED ON THE STORIES "MARTIAN CHRONICLES")

Gerasimenko I.

St. Petersburg University of Management Technologies and Economics, Associate Professor

Abstract

The relevance of the research is determined by the need for a comprehensive study of phraseological units related to the genre of science fiction. The purpose of the study is to analyze Ray Bradbury's phraseological units in a translational aspect. The system of methods includes the method of continuous sampling and comparative lexico-stylistic analysis. Conclusions. The following methods of interlanguage transformation were used in the translation: the method of partial and full equivalent; descriptive; overtone translation; literal translation; omission.

Keywords: phraseological units, translation, interlanguage transformation.

Phraseological units in the works of Ray Bradbury are of considerable interest for scientific research. They allow you to focus the reader's attention on the inner world of the characters, make monologues, dialogues and the plot as a whole more dynamic. However, the idiosyncrasies of the writer and the context of the use of phraseological phrases create difficulties when translating them into Russian.

We have considered the variants of the translation of phraseological units presented by T. N. Shinkar and L. L. Zhdanov in the cycle of stories "Martian Chronicles" [2]. The analysis of the methods of transformation of phraseological units used by the above-mentioned authors was carried out according to the classification of A.V. Kunin [4]. As a result, the following methods were identified: the method of full equivalent; the method of partial equivalent; descriptive method; literal translation (calculus); overtone translation; omission of phraseological turnover in the translation text.

The group of phraseological units, in the translation of which the method of full equivalent is used, usually includes expressions of an international nature based on national traditions, customs and historical facts. The number of such correspondences in the work "Martian Chronicles" is not numerous:

'To the devil with him!' – Gone, and the hell with it!

'Long time no see!' – Haven't seen you for a long time!

'I think we're on the right track now'. "I think we're on the right track."

'Thank the Lord you had your own private rockets'. – Thank God you have your own rockets.

'Now one clock was set in motion, a faint ticking' – One mechanism ticked softly, the input started.

We also noted that when translating phraseological units, additional information was added to them. At the same time, not only the stylistic, but also the emotional coloring of phraseological turns changes. For example, in the cycle of stories "Martian Chronicles" we meet the phraseology 'Out with it, you!', which in translation looks like "Spread it!".

Phraseology 'Out with it!' is defined in Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary' as follows: 'Said to someone when you want them to tell you something they don't want you to know' [5, p.1008]. The Russian verb "to spread out" in accordance with Dmitriev's "Explanatory Dictionary" means "to talk openly and directly about something" [3, p. 103].

When translating phraseological phrases into Russian, in a number of cases, the method of partial equivalent is used. A partial equivalent does not mean any incompleteness in the transmission of meaning, but only contains lexical, grammatical or lexico-grammatical discrepancies in the presence of the same meaning of the same stylistic orientation.

When translating the cycle of stories "The Martian Chronicles", T. N. Shinkar and L. L. Zhdanov try to adhere as closely as possible to the original, observing, among other things, the stylistic orientation of the work. In most of the examples of phraseological units we have studied by the partial equivalent method, they convey the meaning of verbs and participles very accurately, but allow lexical discrepancies in the case of other parts of speech. For example, 'Sir, I thought we might break out rations of gin and meat and whoop it up a bit'. – Boss, it would be nice to open a few cans of gin and meat and have a little fun.